

ENTREPRENEURIAL ORIENTATION AND SME PERFORMANCE: A SEQUENTIAL MEDIATION ANALYSIS OF MARKET AND LEARNING ORIENTATION USING STRUCTURAL EQUATION MODELING

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ABSTRACT

Drawing on the Resource-Based View and the Dynamic Capabilities Theory, this study aims to investigate the effect of entrepreneurial orientation on small and medium-sized enterprises (SME) performance. Additionally, it examines the mediating role of market orientation and learning orientation in the relationship between entrepreneurial orientation and SME performance. Finally, the study explores the sequential mediation effect of market orientation and learning orientation between entrepreneurial orientation and SME performance to understand how the joint mobilization of these strategic resources transforms entrepreneurial actions into superior organizational performance. This study adopts a quantitative approach, using convenience-based non-probability sampling to collect data from 113 managers of Moroccan SMEs operating across various sectors. The collected data are analyzed using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) to test the proposed hypotheses. The results indicate that entrepreneurial orientation has a positive and significant direct effect on the performance of Moroccan SMEs. Furthermore, market orientation partially mediates the relationship between entrepreneurial orientation and SME performance. However, the mediating effect of learning orientation was found to be non-significant in the link between entrepreneurial orientation and SME performance. Finally, the study found the existence of a sequential mediation effect exerted by market orientation and learning orientation in the relationship between entrepreneurial orientation and SME performance. This study is the first to explore the sequential mediating role exercised jointly and successively by market orientation and learning orientation in the relationship between entrepreneurial orientation and SME performance. Notably, the entrepreneurial orientation of SME in Morocco has not been previously studied, offering a valuable contribution to the literature on emerging economies, which remains underexplored in entrepreneurial orientation research. Lastly, a surprising result emerges compared to previous studies: learning orientation does not play a mediating role between entrepreneurial orientation and performance, thus challenging the universality of this mechanism and opening new avenues for research into contextual factors, particularly in SMEs of developing countries.

Keywords: *Entrepreneurial Orientation, Market Orientation, Learning Orientation, Sequential Mediation, SME Performance, Structural Equation Modeling*

INTRODUCTION

Small and medium-sized enterprises play a crucial role in economic and social development by contributing to job creation, inclusive growth, and local economic resilience (EL Hammoumi et al., 2025; Jang & Lee, 2025). In emerging economies, particularly Morocco, these enterprises hold a central position but face numerous structural and contextual challenges that hinder their competitiveness and overall performance (Banque Mondiale, 2024; EL Hammoumi et al., 2025). Given this concerning reality, it is imperative for SME leaders to rethink traditional management models and adopt more innovative strategies (Allammari et al., 2025).

Recent academic literature recommends developing an entrepreneurial orientation as a strategic response to these challenges (Lanivich et al., 2025; Rocha et al., 2025). Indeed, entrepreneurial orientation enables firms to anticipate market developments (Hanif et al., 2024), seize new opportunities (George, 2025), innovate continuously (Sheppard, 2025), enhance resilience (Xia et al., 2024), and improve overall performance (Alulu et al., 2025; Andriani et al., 2024). However, other studies suggest that the beneficial effects of entrepreneurial orientation cannot be fully realized without considering its synergy with other key strategic resources (Hernandez-Perlines et al., 2021).

In this context, this study identifies two additional strategic orientations essential for entrepreneurial orientation: market orientation and learning orientation. Firstly, market orientation links entrepreneurial actions to match the needs of the market and those of competition with respect to greater strategic relevance (Cheng et al., 2025; Yaqub et al., 2024). At the same time, the learning orientation encourages the absorption, diffusion, and adaptation of acquired knowledge, an important factor in transforming the entrepreneurial acts into sustainable competitive advantages (Alyammahi et al., 2024; Ismail et al., 2023). Collectively, these orientations help integrate entrepreneurial activities into unified and strategic processes and thus improve the overall performance of SMEs (Cheng et al., 2025; Poernomo et al., 2025).

Covin and Slevin (1989) describe entrepreneurial orientation as a strategic stance manifesting risk taking and proactiveness and a set of innovation maintaining activities. Innovation allows SMEs to create new products, services and processes and to be more competitive in dynamic markets (Bauweraerts & Colot, 2023; Bottai et al., 2024). Risk taking, especially calculated risks, urges SMEs to follow the unique and audacious strategy rather than traditional managerial practices by introducing new products/services or new markets (Durendez et al., 2023; Ngo & Vu, 2025). Proactiveness enables SMEs to predict the future market trends, to capitalize on the new opportunities, and to undertake strategic initiatives in advance of their rivals (Al-Omouh et al., 2023; Hashem et al., 2024).

Alongside entrepreneurial orientation, market orientation constitutes a major organizational capability centered on the systematic generation of information about customers and competitors, its internal dissemination, and strategic responsiveness (Narver & Slater, 1990). This model encompasses three fundamental aspects: customer orientation, aiming to understand current and future customer needs (Allammari et al., 2024; Bekata & Kero, 2024); competitor orientation, involving active monitoring and analysis of competitors' strategies and actions (Fazal et al., 2023); and interfunctional coordination, ensuring the integration and alignment of different departments for a collective response to market demands (Ajer et al., 2024).

Learning orientation, on the other hand, refers to an enterprise's strategic disposition towards valuing continuous learning, encouraging knowledge sharing, and adapting behaviors based on accumulated experiences for continuous improvement (Calantone et al., 2002; Sinkula et al., 1997). In the same vein, Sinkula's (1997) model integrates three key dimensions of learning orientation: commitment to learning, indicating the priority placed by managers and employees on continuous

knowledge development (Abdelwahed & Basly, 2023); collective open-mindedness, involving regular questioning of established routines and beliefs (Dolbier et al., 2025); and shared vision, representing a common strategic focus on innovation, continuous adaptation, and long-term value creation (Hu et al., 2023).

Drawing on Resource-Based View (Barney, 1991) and Dynamic Capabilities Theory (Teece et al., 1997), this research aims to highlight internal strategic processes enabling SMEs to adapt and enhance their performance in dynamic environments. Accordingly, this study pursues multiple objectives. Firstly, it examines whether entrepreneurial orientation directly improves the performance of Moroccan SMEs. Secondly, it analyzes the mediating role of market orientation and learning orientation in the relationship between entrepreneurial orientation and performance. Thirdly, it explores the interaction between market orientation and learning orientation to determine whether market orientation fosters the development of a learning orientation within these organizations. Furthermore, the study evaluates the existence of a sequential mediation mechanism, whereby entrepreneurial orientation influences performance through market orientation followed by learning orientation.

In this respect, this paper addresses three gaps identified in recent literature. Firstly, while numerous studies have demonstrated the positive impact of entrepreneurial orientation on performance in diverse international contexts, including Asia (Andriani et al., 2024; Jang & Lee, 2025), Latin America (Campos-Nunez & Serrano-Malebran, 2024; dos Santos et al., 2023), Europe (Hernandez-Linares et al., 2023; Suder, 2024), and Sub-Saharan Africa (Khwaee, 2024; Lanivich et al., 2025), no empirical study has yet explored this relationship in the specific context of Moroccan SMEs. Thus, this research contributes by providing original empirical data from an emerging country underrepresented in academic literature.

Secondly, previous studies have often examined the mediating effects of market orientation (e.g., Cheng et al., 2025) or learning orientation (e.g., Ismail et al., 2023) separately and independently. However, this study examines the complementarity between these orientations to better understand how organizational resources interact to transform entrepreneurial orientation into superior performance. This research thus proposes an original sequential mediation model, whereby entrepreneurial orientation stimulates market orientation, which in turn strengthens learning orientation, ultimately enhancing overall SME performance.

Thirdly, although numerous studies have supported the mediating role of learning orientation in the relationship between entrepreneurial orientation and firm performance (e.g., Ismail et al., 2023; Meekeawkhunchorn et al., 2021; Zmegac et al., 2021), these findings are predominantly based on research conducted in developed economies or highly structured organizational environments. However, limited research has examined whether this mediating mechanism holds true in contexts where organizational learning processes may be less formalized, such as in SMEs operating in emerging economies. This study addresses this gap by empirically testing the mediating role of learning orientation within Moroccan SMEs, thereby questioning the universality of this mechanism and extending the conversation to underexplored contexts.

The remainder of this article is structured as follows: the first section presents a literature review and develops the theoretical framework along with the research hypotheses. The second section outlines the methodological framework, detailing the data collection and analysis procedures. Subsequently, the results are presented and discussed in relation to previous research. Finally, the article concludes by summarizing theoretical contributions, practical implications, study limitations, and recommendations for future research.

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND AND HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

Resource-based view and dynamic capabilities theory

The Resource-Based View (RBV), primarily introduced by Barney (1991), posits that sustainable competitive advantage originates from a firm's unique internal resources. According to RBV, these resources must be valuable, rare, difficult to imitate, and non-substitutable to confer competitive advantage (Wernerfelt, 1984; Barney & Clark, 2007). Resources can be tangible, such as equipment and technologies, or intangible, such as organizational competencies, corporate culture, and accumulated knowledge (Barney, 1991).

In the context of SMEs, which frequently face resource constraints, RBV facilitates understanding how strategic orientations serve as internal performance levers (Abdulrab et al., 2022; Lanivich et al., 2025). Thus, entrepreneurial orientation, market orientation, and learning orientation are interpreted as strategic intangible resources that enable SMEs to develop distinctive internal capabilities (Hernández Linares & López Fernandez, 2020).

However, while RBV focuses primarily on possessing valuable resources, it does not explicitly address how firms can adapt or reconfigure these resources over time, particularly in rapidly changing environments (Eisenhardt & Martin, 2000; Teece et al., 2007). To overcome this limitation, the Dynamic Capabilities Theory (DCT), developed by Teece et al., (1997), complements RBV by emphasizing the firm's capacity to continuously integrate, build, and reconfigure internal and external competencies (Zollo & Winter, 2002). According to DCT, competitive advantage arises not only from the possession of valuable resources but also from the firm's dynamic abilities to renew and redeploy these resources effectively in response to market shifts and uncertainty (Teece, 2014).

Within this integrated theoretical framework (RBV and DCT), entrepreneurial orientation represents a strategic resource that provides firms with initial advantages through proactive behaviors, innovation, and risk-taking (Covin & Lumpkin, 2011). Market orientation and learning orientation, in contrast, are considered dynamic capabilities because they allow firms to effectively identify external market changes, seize opportunities, and reconfigure internal processes and knowledge accordingly (Day, 2011; Teece et al., 2007). In other words, these orientations help transform static entrepreneurial resources into dynamic competitive advantages, enabling SMEs to maintain superior organizational performance over time. This combined perspective (RBV-DCT) therefore clarifies how entrepreneurial, market, and learning orientations jointly contribute to SME performance through both resource possession and continuous adaptive mechanisms.

Entrepreneurial orientation and SMEs performance

Entrepreneurial orientation is a well-studied concept in management science, first introduced by Miller (1983) then, developed further by Covin & Slevin (1989) and Lumpkin & Dess (1996). It is realized by proactive, innovative and risk-taking behaviors that allow firms to capitalize on opportunities and to adjust to a constantly evolving environment (Rauch et al., 2009; Wiklund & Shepherd, 2005). The academia extensively acknowledges the relevance of entrepreneurial orientation as key determinant of SME performance, growth, competitive advantage, and sustainability (Hizarci et al., 2023; Stock et al., 2024). The positive association between entrepreneurial orientation and SME performance is well supported by empirical studies. Sajjad et al. (2023) presented enhanced SME level of performance even under the fluctuating dynamics of the entrepreneurial orientation environment. Sturm et al. (2023) accentuate the influence of entrepreneurial orientation on supply chain resilience.

Moreover, cross-national studies further validate this relationship. For instance, Engelen et al., (2015), using data from 790 SMEs across six countries, demonstrated that entrepreneurial orientation has a significant positive impact on firm performance, and that this effect is further strengthened by top managers' transformational leadership behaviors. Similarly, Semrau et al. (2016), in a multilevel analysis of 1,248 SMEs from seven national contexts, confirmed a strong and positive relationship between entrepreneurial orientation and performance across diverse cultural environments, thus reinforcing the generalizability of this link. Other studies of Khan et al. (2021) and Abdulrab et al. (2022) highlight the favorable impact of entrepreneurial orientation on financial and non-financial performance aspects. Eventually, Ma & Yang (2022) and Morgan & Anokhin (2023) indicate the indirect benefits of entrepreneurial orientation on performance through innovation and customer engagement. Within the RBV framework, entrepreneurial orientation is viewed as a unique, rare, and non-substitutable strategic internal resource fostering agility, differentiation, and value creation (Cheng et al., 2025; Kusa et al., 2024). Based on these considerations, this study hypothesizes:

H1: Entrepreneurial orientation positively influences SME performance.

The mediating role of market orientation

While entrepreneurial orientation enables SMEs to initiate innovative, proactive, and risk-taking actions, market orientation channels these efforts toward solutions aligned with market demands (Cheng et al., 2025; Hanaysha & Al-Shaikh, 2024). Firms characterized by strong entrepreneurial and market orientations are better positioned to identify viable opportunities, adapt their commercial strategies, and effectively respond to competitive dynamics (Triani & Yeni, 2023; Yaqub et al., 2024). Consequently, market orientation acts as a mechanism converting entrepreneurial actions into enhanced organizational performance (Cheng et al., 2025).

Literature indicates that few studies have explored the mediating role of market orientation in the relationship between entrepreneurial orientation and SME performance. For example, Moraru et al. (2017), examining Romanian SMEs, found market orientation partially mediates this relationship. Similar findings were reported in Thailand (Chetthamrongchai & Jermstittiparsert, 2020), Oman (Mantok et al., 2019), Indonesia (Ariasih et al., 2018), and Malaysia (Amin et al., 2016). Recently, Cheng et al. (2025) showed in a Chinese context that entrepreneurial orientation significantly fosters market orientation, which in turn mediates performance enhancement.

From RBV perspective (Barney, 1991), market orientation can be conceptualized as a strategic organizational capability complementing entrepreneurial orientation (Yaqub et al., 2024). Their combined utilization ensures more efficient exploitation of internal resources, strengthening overall SME performance (Abdulrab et al., 2022). Therefore, this study hypothesizes:

H2: Market orientation mediates the relationship between entrepreneurial orientation and SME performance.

The mediating role of learning orientation

Entrepreneurial orientation motivates SMEs to innovate, assume risks, and anticipate environmental changes (Covin & Wales, 2012). This process naturally leads firms to learn from their experiences, adjust managerial practices, and consequently develop a learning orientation (Ismail et al., 2023; Wang, 2008). As a result, these enterprises can more effectively exploit market opportunities and enhance organizational performance (Calantone et al., 2002). Thus, learning

orientation acts as a critical mechanism through which entrepreneurial behaviors translate into superior performance outcomes (Al-Shami et al., 2022; Wilson & Perepelkin, 2022).

Empirical validation of the mediating role of learning orientation exists across diverse contexts. For instance, Gomes et al. (2022) demonstrated that learning orientation partially mediates the relationship between entrepreneurial orientation and SME performance in Brazilian SMEs. Similar conclusions were reported in Spain (Real et al., 2014), Pakistan (Hina et al., 2021), India (Mantok et al., 2019), Algeria (Makhloufi et al., 2021), and Southeast Asia (Meekaewkunchorn et al., 2021).

Within the framework of the RBV and its extension, DCT, Teece et al. (1997) argue that merely possessing strategic resources, such as entrepreneurial orientation, is insufficient to ensure sustainable performance. Organizations must also mobilize organizational capabilities that transform, integrate, and adapt these resources to evolving market conditions (Teece et al., 1997). This study posits that such dynamic capabilities can be cultivated through learning orientation, as it facilitates acquiring, integrating, and exploiting new knowledge, thereby enhancing SMEs' adaptability (Alegre et al., 2009; Hernández Linares & López Fernandez, 2020). Accordingly, this study hypothesizes:

H3: Learning orientation mediates the relationship between entrepreneurial orientation and SME performance.

Market orientation as an antecedent of learning orientation

Market orientation, characterized by customer satisfaction, competitor intelligence, and inter-functional coordination (Narver & Slater, 1990), fundamentally promotes a learning-oriented culture (Guerra & Camargo, 2024). By systematically integrating market expectations into decision-making processes, firms establish routines for information gathering, dissemination, and utilization (Baker & Sinkula, 2009). Such practices foster continuous learning dynamics, enabling organizations to adapt more effectively to their environment (Wilson & Liguori, 2023; Yeni et al., 2017).

The literature review indicates limited studies examining the direct effect of market orientation on learning orientation. Guerra and Camargo (2024), through a study involving 309 SME managers in Brazil, demonstrated that market orientation significantly and positively influences the adoption of learning orientation. Similar findings were observed in Indonesia (Hutahayan et al., 2021), Thailand (Phorncharoen, 2020), and Pakistan (Khan & Bashir, 2020), reinforcing the pivotal role of market orientation in enhancing learning capabilities.

From the RBV (Barney, 1991), market orientation functions as an organizational capability transforming market information into actionable learning (Baker & Sinkula, 2009). It thereby supports the development of dynamic capabilities essential for continuously adapting strategic resources to changing environmental demands (Teece et al., 1997). Therefore, this paper hypothesizes:

H4: Market orientation positively influences learning orientation

The sequential mediating role of market orientation and learning orientation

The literature identifies significant bilateral relationships among these variables. Firstly, entrepreneurial orientation positively affects market orientation, as entrepreneurial posture drives SMEs to actively seek information about markets, customers, and competitors (Cheng et

al., 2025; Hanaysha & Al-Shaikh, 2024). Secondly, market orientation enhances learning orientation by encouraging firms to adjust internal practices through strategic intelligence, collective learning, and exploiting market knowledge (Guerra & Camargo, 2024; Hutahayan et al., 2021). Thirdly, learning orientation has shown positive impact on SME performance by fostering innovation, responsiveness, and adaptability (Hina et al., 2021; Real et al., 2014).

Based on these findings, it is theoretically relevant to posit a sequential mediation effect. To the best of our knowledge, no existing study has explored this sequential mediation mechanism, particularly in emerging economies. By proposing this hypothesis, this research aims to deepen understanding of how entrepreneurial orientation effects can be amplified through successive internal mechanisms. This progressive impact process is grounded in the RBV (Barney, 1991) and DCT (Teece et al., 1997), according to which strategic resources (e.g., entrepreneurial orientation) must be combined with organizational capabilities (market orientation, learning orientation) to achieve sustainable competitive advantage (Baker & Sinkula, 2009; Wang, 2008). Consequently, this study hypothesizes:

H5: The relationship between entrepreneurial orientation and SME performance is sequentially mediated by market orientation and learning orientation.

Figure 1 illustrates the conceptual model proposed in this study.

Figure 1. Conceptual Model

METHODS

Instrument

A structured questionnaire was used to collect primary data for this study, as it is a widely accepted tool for examining behavioral and organizational constructs (Tourangeau et al., 2000). All measurement scales were adapted from established instruments in prior research to ensure validity and reliability. The full list of items used to measure each construct is provided in Appendix 1. In total, the questionnaire included 41 items, all evaluated using a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (“strongly disagree”) to 5 (“strongly agree”), except for demographic

variables. Items translated from English to French were rigorously validated by two professors majoring in management sciences to ensure conceptual consistency and clarity.

A 9-item scale for entrepreneurial orientation was adapted from Covin and Slevin (1989), a measurement widely tested and validated in the academic literature (e.g., Li et al., 2009). This construct includes three dimensions: innovativeness, risk-taking, and proactiveness. A 3-item scale was used to measure innovativeness, defined as the firm's capacity to foster creativity and develop new products or services (Covin & Slevin, 1989). A sample item is: "In general, the top managers of our organization favor a strong emphasis on Research & Development, technological leadership, and innovations." The Cronbach's alpha for innovativeness was 0.76 (Li et al., 2009).

A 3-item scale was adopted to measure risk-taking, referring to the company's willingness to commit resources to uncertain yet promising initiatives (Covin & Slevin, 1989). A sample item is: "In general, the top managers of my firm have a strong proclivity for high-risk projects." The Cronbach's alpha for risk-taking was 0.85 (Li et al., 2009).

A 3-item scale was utilized to assess proactiveness, defined as the company's attitude toward anticipating market trends and outperforming competitors (Covin & Slevin, 1989). A sample item is: "In dealing with its competitors, my firm is very often the first business to introduce products/services, administrative techniques, operation technologies, etc". The Cronbach's alpha for proactiveness was 0.78 (Li et al., 2009).

A 12-item scale for market orientation was adapted from Narver and Slater (1990). The construct includes three dimensions: customer orientation, competitor orientation, and inter-functional coordination. A 5-item scale was used to measure customer orientation, defined as "the sufficient understanding of one's target buyers to be able to continuously create superior value for them"(Narver & Slater, 1990, p. 21). A sample item is: "We respond quickly to our customers' needs." The Cronbach's alpha for customer orientation was 0.86 (Narver & Slater, 1990).

A 3-item scale was adopted to measure competitor orientation, which refers to "a seller's understanding of the short-term strengths and weaknesses and long-term capabilities and strategies of both the key current and potential competitors" (Narver & Slater, 1990, p. 21–22). A sample item is: "Top managers discuss competitors' strategies." The Cronbach's alpha for competitor orientation was 0.72 (Narver& Slater, 1990).

A 4-item scale was used for inter-functional coordination, defined as "the coordinated efforts among internal departments to create superior value for customers" (Narver & Slater, 1990, p. 22). A sample item is: "Different departments in our company collaborate effectively to create superior value for target customers." The Cronbach's alpha for inter-functional coordination was 0.73 (Narver & Slater, 1990).

An 11-item scale for learning orientation was adapted from Sinkula et al. (1997) and Calantone et al. (2002). The construct includes three dimensions: commitment to learning, open-mindedness, and shared vision. A 4-item scale was used to measure commitment to learning, defined as "the committed organization considers learning as an important investment that is crucial for survival" (Calantone et al., 2002, p. 516). A sample item is: "Managers basically agree that our organization's ability to learn is key to our competitive advantage." The Cronbach's alpha for commitment to learning was 0.80 (Calantone et al., 2002).

A 3-item scale was adopted to measure open-mindedness, which refers to "the willingness to critically evaluate the organization's operational routine and to accept new ideas" (Calantone et al., 2002, p. 517). A sample item is: "We are not afraid to reflect critically on the shared

assumptions we have made about our customers.” The Cronbach’s alpha for open-mindedness was 0.72 (Calantone et al., 2002).

A 4-item scale was used for shared vision, defined as “wide-focus on organizational members around common values and learning objectives” (Calantone et al., 2002, p. 516). A sample item is: “There is a commonality of purpose in my organization.” The Cronbach’s alpha for shared vision was 0.79 (Calantone et al., 2002).

A 9-item scale for SME performance was adapted from Hughes & Morgan (2007), Slater & Narver (1994), and Wiklund & Shepherd (2005). The construct includes three dimensions: financial performance, commercial performance, and customer performance. The approach of combining three performances is consistent with past studies (Hughes & Morgan, 2007; Slater & Narver, 1994; Wiklund & Shepherd, 2005). A 3-item scale was used to measure financial performance, defined as economic outcomes, such as profitability, return on investment, and profit growth (Wiklund & Shepherd, 2005). A sample item is: “Our company has experienced improved profitability over the past three years.” The Cronbach’s alpha for financial performance was 0.70 (Wiklund & Shepherd, 2005).

A 3-item scale was adopted to measure commercial performance, which refers to market-related outcomes, including sales growth, increased market share, and successful new product launches (Slater & Narver, 1994). A sample item is: “Our sales have grown significantly in recent years.” The Cronbach’s alpha for commercial performance was 0.70 (Slater & Narver, 1994).

A 3-item scale was utilized for customer performance, defined as the company’s ability to attract new customers, retain existing ones, and secure repeat orders (Hughes & Morgan, 2007). A sample item is: “We have been able to attract totally new customers this year.” The Cronbach’s alpha for customer performance was 0.86 (Hughes & Morgan, 2007).

Context

This research was conducted specifically within the context of Moroccan SMEs. These enterprises constitute nearly 97% of the national economic fabric, generate approximately 74% of employment, and contribute 38% to national wealth creation (OMTPME, 2024). Despite their critical role in the country's economic and social development, Moroccan SMEs face growing structural challenges, particularly regarding competitiveness, access to finance, and environmental instability (Yacoubi & Tourabi, 2024). According to the latest report from the Moroccan Observatory of SMEs (2024), formal SME dissolutions increased by 32% between 2021 and 2023 (OMTPME, 2024). Additionally, Allianz Trade (2024) ranks Morocco among countries with the highest rise in business liquidations (Allianz Trade, 2024). Given this concerning context, it becomes imperative to explore managerial strategies that could enhance SME performance in Morocco, notably by strengthening their strategic and organizational orientation. This contextual choice addresses an empirical and theoretical gap insufficiently explored in the literature concerning emerging economies.

Pretest and pilot testing

Prior to the main data collection, a pretest of the questionnaire is conducted to assess clarity, coherence, and comprehension within the Moroccan context. In line with recommendations by Dillman et al. (2014) and Malhotra (2020), a sample of 5 to 10 respondents is sufficient to detect major issues in an instrument. The pretest involved cognitive interviews with two management academic experts and five SME managers, consistent with guidelines by Willis (2004). Feedback has resulted in minor adjustments in wording to ensure practical applicability and clarity.

Subsequently, a pilot test is implemented with 20 SME managers from various sectors (industry, services, commerce), aligning with methodological recommendations suggesting a minimum of 15 to 30 respondents for initial reliability testing (Malhotra, 2020). Data analysis indicates Cronbach's alpha coefficients above 0.70 for all variables, confirming good internal reliability and validating the questionnaire for broader distribution.

Sampling technique

In the Moroccan environment, linking directly with SME managers is often limited by their availability, geographical separation and sensitivity to divulge strategic information (Allammari et al., 2025; Yacoubi & Tourabi, 2024). Therefore, this study uses non-probability convenience sampling that is recommended under conditions of scarce resources and exploratory research (Etikan et al., 2016; Sinha et al., 2019). This sampling design is widely used in research on SMEs in emerging economies as well (Keelson et al., 2024).

Explicit inclusion criteria were defined, restricting participation exclusively to Moroccan SME managers operating in the industry, services, or commerce sectors, with a minimum tenure of three years in their respective companies. This criterion aims to ensure response relevance and reliability. Furthermore, only enterprises meeting the official SME definition established by the Moroccan Observatory of VSEs and SMEs (OMTPME, 2024) were included. According to this definition, SMEs are firms with an annual turnover ranging between 10 and 175 million dirhams and employee numbers from 10 to 200. These criteria were systematically employed to reflect targeted enterprises.

Data collection

For data collection, an online questionnaire was designed using Google Forms. The questionnaire included an introductory message clearly stating the study's objectives, guaranteeing respondent anonymity, and indicating an estimated completion time of approximately ten minutes, in line with methodological guidelines proposed by Dillman et al. (2014) for online survey design.

The participant recruitment process involved three distinct phases. Initially, personalized messages were dispatched to SME managers via LinkedIn, a platform commonly employed for academic research surveys (Bantha & Nayak, 2023; Sutherland & Jarrahi, 2018). Although 120 questionnaires were disseminated using this method, only ten usable responses were obtained, highlighting challenges such as limited availability and heightened sensitivity towards information disclosure within the Moroccan SME context (Yacoubi & Tourabi, 2024).

Subsequently, face-to-face visits were arranged with selected SMEs, directly requesting meetings with senior managers. Despite facing constraints including respondent unavailability and reluctance to participate, this approach led an additional ten valid responses. In-person data collection is recommended in low online-response environments as it enhances data quality and reliability (Bryman, 2016).

Finally, to expand the sample and facilitate data collection, a scientific research agreement was established with two Moroccan professional associations: the Moroccan Association of the Procurement Community¹ and the Business Managers Club². With active support from their respective research committees, direct and personalized invitations were sent to their members,

¹<https://amca.ma/>

²<https://www.clubdesdirigeants.ma/>

encouraging participation. This initiative resulted in distributing 250 invitations, generating 112 completed responses.

The entire data collection process spanned approximately four months. Overall, 380 questionnaires were administered, resulting in 137 responses, of which 113 met the inclusion criteria. Consequently, the final response rate was approximately 36%, considered acceptable for surveys targeting business managers (Baruch & Holtom, 2008; Fincham, 2008).

Sample Size

A power analysis was conducted using G*Power software (version 3.1.9.7), adhering to guidelines established by Faul et al. (2009). Assuming a significance level of 5%, statistical power of 90%, a medium effect size ($f^2 = 0.15$), and three predictors, G*Power suggested a minimum sample size of 99 observations. Thus, the final sample size of 113 SMEs adequately meets and surpasses these minimum requirements, ensuring robust statistical validity.

Table 1 presents the demographic profile of the respondents. The majority of participants were male (75.2%), which reflects the gender structure of SME ownership and management in Morocco, where leadership roles are predominantly held by men (HCP, 2021; World Bank, 2020). Most were aged between 30 and 39 years (60.2%). Over half of the respondents held at least a Bachelor's degree (54.9%), and 84.1% occupied managerial positions. In terms of tenure, 41.6% had between 5 and 10 years of experience. Most firms surveyed were small-sized enterprises with fewer than 50 employees (54.9%), and the industrial sector was the most represented (47.8%).

Common method bias

To ensure that the study's outcomes were not influenced by common method bias or multicollinearity issues, two methodological tests were conducted, following guidelines from Hair et al. (2019), Kock (2015), and Podsakoff et al. (2003). Firstly, variant inflation factors (VIF) were computed for all latent variable indicators. The results revealed VIF values ranging between 1.4 and 2.8, below the critical threshold of 3.30 (Hair et al., 2019; Kock, 2015), indicating no significant multicollinearity within the model.

Secondly, Harman's single-factor test was performed to detect potential common method bias within self-reported responses (Harman, 1976). An exploratory factor analysis (EFA) using principal component analysis without rotation was conducted on all items using SPSS. The results indicated eight distinct factors with eigen values above 1, with the first factor explaining only 39.34% of total variance. This value is significantly below the 50% critical threshold recommended by MacKenzie and Podsakoff (2012), thereby mitigating concerns regarding common method bias.

DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Initially, descriptive analysis and correlation analysis were conducted, followed by a confirmatory analysis utilizing the Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) method through SmartPLS 4.0 (Ringle et al., 2022). Following recommendations by Chin (1998) and Hair et al. (2019), this procedure was structured in two primary phases: first, the assessment of the measurement model to verify the validity and reliability of constructs, and second, the evaluation of the structural model to test the hypothesized relationships.

Table 1: Demographic Profile (n=113)

Attribute	Category	Frequency	%
Gender	Male	85	75.2
	Female	28	24.8
Age	Under 30 years	19	16.8
	30–39 years	68	60.2
	40–49 years	18	15.9
	50 years and above	8	7.1
Position held	Top manager	95	84.1
	Senior manager	18	15.9
Experience in current organization	Less than 5 years	25	22.1
	5–10 years	47	41.6
	More than 10 years	41	36.3
Education level	Bachelor's degree	62	54.9
	Master's degree	48	42.5
	Doctorate	3	2.7
Firm size	Small	62	54.9
	Medium	51	45.1
Industry sector	Industry	54	47.8
	Services	38	33.6
	Commerce	21	18.6

Correlations and summary statistics

Given the extensive number of dimensions per construct, a comprehensive correlation analysis was deemed impractical. Therefore, in alignment with recommendations by Sarstedt et al. (2019), mean scores were calculated for each primary variable using SPSS to streamline analysis.

Results indicate mean scores ranging from 3.50 to 3.91, reflecting a general respondent agreement. Standard deviations, between 0.67 and 0.89, show moderate response variability. All Pearson correlations among variables were significant at the 0.01 level, with coefficients exceeding 0.5. Particularly strong correlations emerged between market orientation and performance ($r = 0.740$), and between market orientation and organizational learning ($r = 0.684$), highlighting substantial associations and confirming their potential contribution to SME performance.

Assessment of measurement model

The measurement model assessment aimed to verify the psychometric quality of instruments used to measure latent constructs (Hair et al., 2019). Consistent with Chin (1998) and Hair et al. (2017), this evaluation comprises three critical stages: internal consistency reliability, convergent validity, and discriminant validity.

Internal consistency reliability indicates the homogeneity of items measuring a latent construct (Hair et al., 2017; Richter et al., 2016). It is generally assessed using Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability (Henseler et al., 2009; Richter et al., 2016). Values above 0.70 for both

indicators are acceptable as per Nunnally (1978) and Hair et al. (2019). In this study, all latent variables exhibited Cronbach's alpha values between 0.73 and 0.84, and composite reliability values exceeding 0.73, confirming internal consistency and robustness of measurement instruments (Table 2).

Convergent validity assesses whether indicators of the same construct converge to measure a shared theoretical concept (Hair et al., 2019). It relies primarily on average variance extracted (AVE) and factor loadings (Hair et al., 2017). Factor loadings greater than 0.70 indicate satisfactory contributions of indicators to their constructs (Chin, 1998), while AVE above 0.50 suggests that the construct explains over 50% of variance in its indicators, affirming good convergent validity (Hair et al., 2017). Here, all factor loadings exceeded 0.70, and AVE values ranged from 0.73 to 0.87, demonstrating adequate convergence of items to respective constructs as illustrated in Table 2.

Discriminant validity (DV) ensures that each latent construct is distinct from other constructs in the model (Hair et al., 2017; Henseler et al., 2015). DV was assessed using the Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT), in accordance with recent methodological guidelines for PLS-SEM (Hair et al., 2021; Henseler et al., 2015). HTMT values below 0.85 typically indicate good discriminant validity (Kline, 2023), although thresholds up to 0.90 may be contextually acceptable (Hair & Alamer, 2022; Henseler et al., 2015). Results are summarized in Table 3. All HTMT values were below the critical threshold of 0.90. The highest values pertained to the pairs IC-CPO (0.882), SV-COM (0.890), and CUP-PR (0.875), which, although close to the threshold, remained within acceptable limits. All the other values were below 0.85. Consequently, discriminant validity criteria were fully met in this study.

Structural Model Evaluation and Hypothesis Testing

The evaluation of the structural model was conducted in two primary steps. The first step entailed verifying the model's quality and predictive power using four indicators: the coefficient of determination R^2 (Chin, 1998), the effect size f^2 (Cohen, 1988), the predictive power assessed via PLSpredict (Shmueli et al., 2019), and the global goodness-of-fit index Gof (Tenenhaus et al., 2004). The second step involved testing the research hypotheses utilizing the path coefficient (β) and P-value (Hair et al., 2017; Henseler et al., 2009).

Model Quality and Predictive Power

The coefficient of determination (R^2) assesses the explanatory capacity of independent variables within the research model (Cohen, 1988). According to the thresholds proposed by Croutche (2002), an R^2 value greater than 0.26 is considered significant. In this study, entrepreneurial orientation accounted for 27.7% of the variance in market orientation. Together, these two variables explain 50.4% of the variance in learning orientation. Finally, the combined effect of these three independent variables explains 67.4% of the variance in SME performance, demonstrating strong explanatory power for the model.

Effect size (f^2) evaluates the relative influence of each exogenous variable on a given endogenous variable (Cohen, 1988). Established thresholds indicate that an f^2 value above 0.35 signifies a strong effect, between 0.15 and 0.35 a medium effect, and between 0.02 and 0.15 a weak effect (Cohen, 1988). This study observed two strong effects: entrepreneurial orientation on market orientation ($f^2 = 0.383$) and market orientation on learning orientation ($f^2 = 0.472$). Medium effects were found for the relationships between entrepreneurial orientation and SME performance ($f^2 = 0.185$), and between market orientation and SME performance ($f^2 = 0.246$). Weak effects were noted for the relationship between entrepreneurial orientation and

organizational learning orientation ($f^2 = 0.071$), as well as between organizational learning orientation and SME performance ($f^2 = 0.105$).

Table 2: Convergent Validity and Internal Consistency Reliability

Variables	Items	Loading	CR	AVE
Innovativeness	IN1	0.850	0.809	0.721
	IN2	0.822		
	IN3	0.874		
Risk-taking	RT1	0.869	0.786	0.695
	RT2	0.845		
	RT3	0.785		
Proactiveness	PR1	0.809	0.738	0.657
	PR2	0.833		
	PR3	0.789		
Commitment	COM1	0.733	0.844	0.666
	COM2	0.799		
	COM3	0.869		
	COM4	0.858		
Open- Mindedness	OPM1	0.850	0.824	0.740
	OPM2	0.869		
	OPM3	0.861		
Shared Vision	SV1	0.844	0.842	0.674
	SV2	0.789		
	SV3	0.845		
	SV4	0.804		
	SV5	0.804		
Customer Orientation	CO1	0.707	0.855	0.621
	CO2	0.767		
	CO3	0.853		
	CO4	0.834		
	CO5	0.770		
Competitor Orientation	CPO1	0.849	0.836	0.750
	CPO2	0.876		
	CPO3	0.874		
Interfunctional Coordination	IC1	0.871	0.847	0.681
	IC2	0.803		
	IC3	0.803		
	IC4	0.794		
Financial Performance	FP1	0.809	0.755	0.670
	FP2	0.833		
	FP3	0.789		
Commercial Performance	CP1	0.877	0.833	0.745
	CP 2	0.835		
	CP 3	0.876		
Customer Performance	CUP1	0.827	0.794	0.707
	CUP 2	0.839		
	CUP 3	0.744		

Table 3: Discriminant Validity (HTMT Criterion)

	CP	COM	CPO	CO	CUP	FP	IN	IC	OPM	PR	RT	SV
CP												
COM	0.701											
CPO	0.686	0.601										
CO	0.723	0.669	0.788									
CUP	0.840	0.735	0.645	0.747								
FP	0.832	0.641	0.642	0.712	0.809							
IN	0.584	0.530	0.643	0.561	0.749	0.659						
IC	0.761	0.705	0.882	0.756	0.770	0.700	0.500					
OPM	0.624	0.596	0.469	0.523	0.568	0.582	0.451	0.481				
PR	0.726	0.607	0.582	0.567	0.875	0.730	0.799	0.532	0.407			
RT	0.443	0.512	0.476	0.468	0.649	0.575	0.830	0.366	0.282	0.898		
SV	0.678	0.890	0.642	0.586	0.674	0.585	0.520	0.773	0.580	0.623	0.455	

Note: CP=Commercial performance, COM=Commitment, CPO=Competitor orientation, CO=Customer orientation, CUP= Customer performance, FP=Financial performance, IN=Innovativeness, IC=Interfunctional coordination, OPM=Open-mindedness, PR=proactiveness, RT=Risk taking, SV=Shared vision

The predictive power of the model was assessed using the PLSpredict procedure, in accordance with the recommendations of Shmueli et al. (2019). The results are reported in Table 4.

To begin with, the Q^2 values were examined and found to be positive for all indicators, demonstrating the model’s predictive relevance. Subsequently, the root mean square error (RMSE) values from the PLS-SEM model were compared to those obtained from a benchmark linear regression model (LM). According to the criteria established by Shmueli et al. (2019), a model demonstrates strong predictive power when the RMSE values from PLS-SEM are consistently lower than those of the LM model across all indicators. As shown in Table 3, the differences between PLS-SEM_RMSE and LM_RMSE are negative for all indicators, confirming that prediction errors are systematically lower under the PLS-SEM approach. Thus, the proposed model can be regarded as having high predictive power.

The global goodness-of-fit index (Gof) assesses overall model fit by integrating the measurement model quality and structural model fit (Tenenhaus et al., 2004). Gof is computed based on the geometric mean of the average R^2 and the average AVE (Fernandes, 2012). According to Wetzels et al. (2009), a Gof exceeding 0.36 indicates a good model fit. This study achieved a Gof of 0.507, with an average R^2 of 0.485 and an average AVE of 0.531, thus confirming a satisfactory overall model fit.

Hypothesis Testing

The study’s hypotheses concerning the direct and indirect effects of entrepreneurial orientation on SME performance were tested using the bootstrap procedure, in accordance with the recommendations of Hair et al. (2019). The results are presented in Table 5 and illustrated in Figure 2.

The analysis of direct effects reveals statistically significant relationships. Entrepreneurial orientation has a direct and positive effect on SME performance ($\beta = 0.298$; $t = 3.734$; $p < 0.001$), thereby confirming Hypothesis H1 at a significance level below 1%. This result suggests that developing an entrepreneurial posture, based on innovativeness, risk-taking, and proactiveness, constitutes a strategic lever for enhancing overall SME performance. Similarly, a comparable result is observed for Hypothesis H4: market orientation has a significant and positive effect on

learning orientation ($\beta = 0.569$; $t = 6.603$; $p < 0.001$). These findings confirm the role of market orientation in fostering internal learning dynamics within SMEs.

Table 4: PLSpredict

Construct	Items	Q ² predict	PLS-SEM_RMSE	LM_RMSE	(PLS - LM)
Commitment	COM1	0.152	0.748	0.782	-0.034
	COM2	0.051	0.910	0.930	-0.020
	COM3	0.192	0.969	1.044	-0.075
	COM4	0.183	0.986	1.037	-0.051
Open-mindedness	OPM1	0.056	0.967	1.004	-0.037
	OPM2	0.109	0.993	1.023	-0.030
	OPM3	0.059	0.852	0.883	-0.031
Shared Vision	SV1	0.111	0.908	0.897	0.011
	SV2	0.141	0.962	1.008	-0.046
	SV3	0.224	0.928	0.935	-0.007
	SV4	0.063	0.969	0.971	-0.002
Customer Orientation	CO1	0.098	0.734	0.774	-0.040
	CO2	0.110	0.799	0.825	-0.027
	CO3	0.156	0.832	0.915	-0.083
	CO4	0.096	0.892	0.952	-0.060
	CO5	0.160	0.794	0.866	-0.073
Competitor Orientation	CPO1	0.190	0.949	1.015	-0.066
	CPO2	0.116	0.997	1.066	-0.069
	CPO3	0.216	0.948	1.051	-0.103
Interfunctional Coordination	IC1	0.114	0.986	0.990	-0.004
	IC2	0.113	0.940	0.965	-0.025
	IC3	0.134	0.922	0.958	-0.036
	IC4	0.031	1.009	1.034	-0.025
Customer Performance	CUP1	0.294	0.617	0.615	0.002
	CUP2	0.203	0.763	0.821	-0.059
	CUP3	0.274	0.724	0.773	-0.049
Commercial Performance	CP1	0.286	0.876	0.944	-0.068
	CP2	0.141	0.853	0.856	-0.003
	CP3	0.119	0.862	0.871	-0.009
Financial Performance	FP1	0.198	0.799	0.898	-0.100
	FP2	0.232	0.763	0.843	-0.080
	FP3	0.216	0.861	0.917	-0.057

Table 5: Results of hypothesis testing

Hypothesis	β	S.D.	t	p	LLCI	ULCI	Decision
TE EO→P	0.647	0.073	8.856	0.000	0.230	0.484	Supported
H1 EO→P	0.298	0.080	3.734	0.000	0.139	0.451	Supported
H2 EO→MO→P	0.212	0.054	3.927	0.000	0.108	0.319	Supported
H3 EO→LO→P	0.058	0.040	1.436	0.151	0.006	0.160	Not Supported
H4 MO → LO	0.569	0.086	6.603	0.000	0.387	0.723	Supported
H5 EO→MO→LO→P	0.078	0.032	2.429	0.015	0.026	0.151	Supported

Note(s): TE = Total Effect; EO = entrepreneurial orientation, P = SME performance, MO = market orientation, LO = learning orientation.

Regarding the mediation analysis, the results demonstrate that the total effect of entrepreneurial orientation on SME performance is significant ($\beta = 0.647$; $t = 8.856$; $p = 0.000$), indicating an overall positive influence. After introducing the mediating variables, the direct effect remains significant ($\beta = 0.298$; $t = 3.734$; $p = 0.000$), suggesting the presence of partial mediation.

H2 is supported at a significance level below 1% ($\beta = 0.212$; $t = 3.927$; $p = 0.000$), indicating that market orientation partially mediates the relationship between entrepreneurial orientation and performance. This finding highlights the central role of a market-oriented culture in converting entrepreneurial dynamics into superior performance outcomes. Conversely, the mediating effect of learning orientation is not statistically significant ($\beta = 0.058$; $t = 1.436$; $p = 0.151$), leading to the rejection of Hypothesis H3. This result suggests that, within the context of this study, entrepreneurial behaviors alone are not sufficient to activate organizational learning processes capable of directly enhancing performance. Moreover, the results reveal a significant sequential mediation effect between entrepreneurial orientation and performance, through market orientation followed by learning orientation ($\beta = 0.078$; $t = 2.429$; $p = 0.015$). Thus, Hypothesis H5 is supported. This result confirms the joint role of market orientation and learning orientation as key mechanisms for transforming entrepreneurial actions into superior performance outcomes.

Figure 2: Structural Model

DISCUSSION AND IMPLICATIONS

The previous results confirm hypothesis H1, suggesting that entrepreneurial orientation positively and directly influences SME performance. This implies that SMEs adopting entrepreneurial behaviors such as innovativeness, risk-taking, and proactiveness are better equipped to manage environmental disruptions, identify new opportunities, and improve overall performance. This conclusion aligns with studies by Rauch et al. (2009), Engelen et al. (2015), and more recently, Cheng et al. (2025). Therefore, in a context like Morocco, where SMEs operate in uncertain and competitive environments, adopting an entrepreneurial stance is not only relevant but necessary for ensuring business survival and sustainability.

Similarly, results confirm hypothesis H2, indicating that market orientation partially mediates the relationship between entrepreneurial orientation and SME performance. This suggests that some benefits of entrepreneurial behaviors do not directly enhance performance but first foster market orientation. In other words, entrepreneurial orientation encourages SMEs to better understand customer needs and monitor their competitive environment, thereby improving their

organizational performance. This finding corroborates previous research by Cheng et al. (2025), Chetthamrongchai and Jermstittiparsert (2020), and Mantok et al. (2019), who emphasize market orientation as a strategic lever for SMEs to adjust offerings, anticipate customer expectations, and increase competitiveness.

Conversely, results do not validate hypothesis H3, indicating that learning orientation does not significantly mediate between entrepreneurial orientation and SME performance. Thus, in the Moroccan context, entrepreneurial behaviors do not seem to directly foster sufficient learning processes to influence performance. This finding contrasts with previous research by Kazemi et al. (2023), Real et al. (2014), and Wang (2008). This unexpected result could be explained by specific contextual characteristics of Moroccan SMEs, including low formalization levels of learning processes (EL Hammoumi et al., 2025), managerial culture not oriented towards knowledge sharing (Lebdaoui et al., 2024), or an unstable economic environment necessitating more immediate adaptation mechanisms (Lamssarbi & Bouaziz, 2024). Thus, although organizational learning is recognized as a strategic lever in other contexts, its impact appears limited in the value-creation chain here, opening interesting avenues for future research.

The results related to hypothesis H4 indicate that market orientation positively predicts learning orientation. This suggests that companies are attentive to changing customer needs, competitor actions, and internal coordination are more likely to develop continuous learning routines. Indeed, strong market orientation prompts SMEs to collect, share, and integrate relevant environmental information, fostering adaptive learning behaviors. This finding aligns with conclusions by Guerra and Camargo (2024), Hutahayan et al. (2021), and Khan and Bashir (2020), who highlight that market-oriented companies are more inclined to cultivate a learning culture. Hence, the market is a key element in developing a culture oriented towards organizational learning.

Finally, a notable result of this study is the validation of hypothesis H5, revealing that market orientation and learning orientation sequentially mediate the relationship between entrepreneurial orientation and SME performance. This suggests that entrepreneurial behaviors alone are insufficient to enhance performance but must be supported by two key organizational dynamics: exploration (market orientation) and exploitation (learning orientation). On one hand, market orientation enables companies to actively explore their external environment, identify emerging customer needs, and monitor competitive developments. On the other hand, learning orientation facilitates the internal exploitation of this information through knowledge assimilation, sharing, and integration processes.

This conclusion strengthens the theoretical contributions related to the organizational ambidexterity model (March, 1991), where the capability to combine exploration and exploitation constitutes a source of sustainable performance, particularly in turbulent environments. It also aligns with the dynamic capabilities perspective (Teece et al., 1997), highlighting that entrepreneurial orientation exerts its effects when mediated by internal adaptation and learning mechanisms. To our knowledge, no previous study has examined this entire mediation chain. However, prior research has separately tested mediations by market orientation (e.g., Cheng et al., 2025; Mantok et al., 2019) and learning orientation (e.g., Kazemi et al., 2023; Gomes et al., 2022). Thus, our findings enrich the literature by providing an integrated view of these two mediators and emphasizing their complementarity.

Practical implications

This study offers several implications for SME managers and policymakers. Firstly, entrepreneurial orientation has been identified as a key factor in improving SME performance.

Therefore, SME leaders should promote an organizational culture centered around innovation, calculated risk-taking, and proactiveness. Practically, this involves implementing internal processes to facilitate creativity (e.g., innovation-focused brainstorming groups), encouraging individual initiatives, and adopting tools that enable anticipation of market changes. Additionally, policymakers could support these efforts by facilitating access to funding for innovative projects or easing administrative constraints for SMEs actively adopting an entrepreneurial stance.

Secondly, the study reveals that market orientation acts as a significant lever enhancing the impact of entrepreneurial orientation on performance. Thus, it is essential for SME managers to develop regular and concrete mechanisms for collecting and analyzing customer and competitor data. For instance, companies could establish systematic strategic monitoring procedures or periodic customer surveys to rapidly adjust their offerings. On a policy level, specific training programs in competitive intelligence and market research practices could be offered to SMEs to strengthen their market adaptation capabilities.

Thirdly, the study validates the positive effect of market orientation on learning orientation. Hence, managers should structure internal processes promoting the exchange of market-derived knowledge. For example, organizing regular inter-departmental meetings focused on customer feedback, market trends, and competitor practices could significantly enhance their learning capacity. Policymakers could further encourage such practices by incentivizing continuous training and inter-company collaboration on best learning practices.

Finally, the study highlights a sequential mediation involving both market orientation and learning orientation. Managers should therefore adopt a clearly articulated two-phase strategy: firstly, proactively identifying market needs, and secondly, integrating this information into internal learning and continuous improvement processes. Specifically, managers can formalize these two phases within a clear internal strategic framework, integrating specific market exploration procedures followed by regular collective learning sessions. Policymakers could support these initiatives by creating support networks facilitating market information transfer to SMEs and encouraging collaborative platforms where companies share and capitalize on learning experiences.

Theoretical Implications

This study provides several original contributions to the literature on entrepreneurial orientation, organizational capabilities, and SME performance. Firstly, it leverages the Resource-Based View (Barney, 1991) and dynamic capabilities theory (Teece et al., 1997) in a context still relatively unexplored, that of Moroccan SMEs. The study demonstrates that entrepreneurial orientation, as a strategic resource, must be coupled with specific organizational capabilities, namely market orientation and learning orientation to generate competitive advantages and sustainable performance. This theoretical positioning enhances understanding of how internal resources translate into performance in emerging environments.

Secondly, the study introduces and empirically validates a grounding sequential mediation mechanism involving market orientation and learning orientation in the relationship between entrepreneurial orientation and SME performance. While previous research has often treated these variables as independent mediators, this work shows that their successive combination strengthens the impact of entrepreneurial orientation. This theoretical contribution moves beyond fragmented interpretations of mediating effects and proposes a systemic view of organizational capabilities in the value-creation chain.

Thirdly, contrary to results frequently reported in the literature (Real et al., 2014; Wang, 2008), our findings show that learning orientation does not play a significant direct mediating role between entrepreneurial orientation and performance. This finding challenges the universality of this mechanism and highlights the importance of contextual factors, particularly within SMEs in developing countries where learning processes are less formalized. This divergence opens new theoretical avenues and calls for a recontextualization of classic organizational learning models.

Fourthly, this research addresses an empirical gap in the literature on SMEs in emerging economies by providing results specific to the Moroccan context. Few studies have analyzed interactions among the three strategic orientations and SME performance within the African continent. Thus, the study provides a contextualized perspective for researchers interested in entrepreneurial dynamics in the Global South.

Finally, the research highlights the complementarity between exploration and exploitation in the process of capability transformation. By demonstrating that market orientation (exploration) fuels learning orientation (exploitation), this study contributes to the organizational ambidexterity literature (March, 1991; O'Reilly III & Tushman, 2013) and proposes a clear sequence of these two dynamics, rarely empirically operationalized within the context of SMEs.

Thus, these contributions offer new theoretical perspectives while emphasizing the importance of the specific context of Moroccan SMEs, enriching current discussions on entrepreneurial and organizational dynamics in emerging economies.

LIMITATIONS AND RESEARCH PERSPECTIVES

Although this study significantly contributes to understanding the mechanisms through which entrepreneurial orientation influences SME performance, it presents several methodological and theoretical limitations that deserve attention. First, the use of convenience non-probabilistic sampling, though suitable for exploratory research with limited resources, reduces the statistical representativeness of the findings. Future research could employ probabilistic or stratified sampling methods to enhance the generalizability of the results to all Moroccan SMEs or similar contexts.

Second, the cross-sectional data collection limits the ability to establish causality between variables. A longitudinal approach would enable the examination of delayed or evolving effects of strategic orientations on performance and a better understanding of organizational learning dynamics over time. Third, this study relies solely on self-reported data from managers, potentially introducing social desirability bias or subjective perception bias. Integrating secondary data sources (objective financial indicators, employee or customer evaluations) would enrich and triangulate results, improving reliability.

Finally, the absence of a significant mediating effect of organizational learning orientation, contrary to many previous studies, raises interesting contextual questions. Future research should explore specific cultural, managerial, or structural factors within Moroccan SMEs that might hinder the impact of organizational learning on performance.

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APPENDIX 1: QUESTIONNAIRE ITEMS

Entrepreneurial Orientation (Covin & Slevin, 1989)

Innovativeness

- In general, the top managers of our organization favor a strong emphasis on Research & Development, technological leadership, and innovations.
- In the past 3 years, our organization has marketed a large variety of new lines of products or services.
- In the past 3 years, changes in our products or service lines have usually been quite dramatic.

Proactiveness

- In dealing with competitors, our organization often leads the competition, initiating actions to which our competitors have to respond.
- In dealing with competitors, our organization is very often the first business to introduce new products/services, administrative techniques, operating technologies, etc.
- In dealing with its competitors, my firm typically adopts a very competitive, 'undo the-competitors' posture.

Risk Taking

- In general, the top managers of my organization have a strong propensity for high-risk projects (with chances of very high return).
- In general, the top managers of my firm believe that owing to the nature of the environment, bold, wide-ranging acts are necessary to achieve the firm's objectives.
- When confronted with decision-making situations involving uncertainty, my firm typically adopts a bold, aggressive posture in order to maximize the probability of exploiting potential opportunities

Market Orientation (Narver & Slater, 1990)

Customer Orientation

- Our business objectives are driven primarily by customer satisfaction.
- Our strategy for competitive advantage is based on our understanding of customers' needs.
- Our business strategies are driven by our beliefs about how we can create greater value for customers.
- We measure customer satisfaction systematically and frequently.
- We give close attention to after-sales service.

Competitor Orientation

- Our salespeople regularly share information within our business concerning competitors' strategies.
- We rapidly respond to competitive actions that threaten us.
- Top management regularly discusses competitors' strengths and strategies.

Interfunctional Coordination

- Employees from different departments regularly participate in joint visits or calls with customers.
- Customer and market information is systematically shared across all functional areas of our firm.
- All functions are involved in the development and integration of our firm's market strategies.
- Each business function contributes actively to delivering superior value to our customers.

Learning Orientation (Sinkula et al., 1997)

Commitment to Learning

- Managers basically agree that our organization's ability to learn is the key to our competitive advantage.
- The basic values of this organization include learning as key to improvement.
- The sense around here is that employee learning is an investment, not an expense.
- Learning in my organization is seen as a key commodity necessary to guarantee organizational survival.

Shared Vision

- There is a commonality of purpose in my organization.
- There is total agreement on our organizational vision across all levels, functions, and divisions.

- All employees are committed to the goals of this organization.
- Employees view themselves as partners in charting the direction of the organization.

Open-Mindedness

- We are not afraid to reflect critically on the shared assumptions we have made about our customers.
- Personnel in this enterprise realize that the very way they perceive the marketplace must be continually questioned.
- We rarely collectively question our own biases about the way we interpret customer information.

SMEs Performance

Financial Performance (Wiklund & Shepherd, 2005)

- Our company has experienced improved profitability over the past three years.
- Our company has experienced improved return on investment over the past three years.
- Our company has experienced improved cash flow over the past three years.

Commercial Performance (Slater & Narver, 1994)

- Our sales have grown significantly in recent years.
- Our market share has increased over the past few years.
- Our new product launches have been commercially successful.

Customer Performance (Hughes & Morgan, 2007)

- We have been able to attract totally new customers this year.
- We have been able to retain our existing customers.
- We have secured repeat orders from our customers.

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